

DEVELOPMENT OF MINCED MEAT WITH INCREASED NUTRITIONAL VALUE**Vasyukova A.,***Professor, doctor of technical sciences,***Moshkin A.,***Technologist, candidate of technical sciences,***Talbi M.***Graduate student**Russian Biotechnology University***Abstract**

Research background. Minced meat is positioned as dietary, which allows it to be used in the production of semi-finished products for specialized nutrition of various contingents, with some types of therapy. The rationale for the choice of minced meat is the wide reserve opportunities in the production of various meat semi-finished products (cutlets, medallions, balls, sticks, etc.).

Experimental approach. The possibility of using minced meat as an object of research for the development of a new meat-growing product using vegetable raw materials is considered. The aim of the research is to develop a combined minced meat with the use of algae as plant components.

Results and conclusions. The development of minced meat makes it possible to introduce algae into the composition of the prescription product and enrich the meat raw materials (beef, pork, lamb, duck and chicken). Using the method of mathematical modeling, the best composition of minced meat was revealed. Based on search experiments to determine the optimal recipes and technology modes of minced binary compositions, including algae and meat raw materials, the most significant factors and levels of their variation were determined. Regression analysis of the dependencies $Y_i = f(X_1, X_2, X_3)$ was carried out and mathematical models of organoleptic evaluation of minced binary compositions were constructed depending on the amount of added protein product (algae), the mass fraction of moisture in minced binary compositions and the duration of their grinding. The composition of binary compositions includes beef, pork, chicken, duck and from 10 to 30 % algae. In the studied vegetable minced meat with algae, the theoretical nutritional digestibility of the finished product increases by 10 %. The conducted studies show that minced meat with the addition of algae in an amount of 30 % to the mass of meat raw materials contributes to an increase in the VUS (water-holding capacity) of minced compositions by 10 %. Organoleptic evaluation of them using a five-point scale made it possible not only to assess the quality level of minced binary compositions, but also to obtain mathematical models that allow determining the optimal values of factors - concentration (C), mass fraction of moisture (W) and duration of grinding of the binary system (T). It was found that in minced binary compositions made according to the optimal regime, the number of essential amino acids significantly increased. Only

Keywords: fermentation, malt, improvers, amylolytic activity, cereals, food products.

Introduction.

Research carried out in the field of improving the quality of food products by their mutual enrichment in the selection of components of the formulation, which are equivalent to supplementing nutritional value and organoleptic indicators. This problem is relevant both for Russia and for any other country in the world.

The issues of compatibility of meat and vegetable raw materials are considered in a number of publications. So Mikhaleva E.V. and Reneva Yu.A. (1) offer meat-vegetable dietary minced meat with the addition of 10% vegetable mixture. Karpunina L. I., Kochneva S. V. (2) proposed combined chopped meat semi-finished products for functional purposes, which are products of a high degree of readiness, which in modern conditions makes them very popular for the consumer. The main purpose of using functional products is to improve the taste properties; partial replacement of meat raw materials; improvement of physical and chemical parameters; reduction of the caloric content of the product, which as a result allows these products to be classified as dietary (3). An important task in obtaining a combined food product is the improvement of existing technologies (4), modeling and optimization of the composition of the formulation of minced meat (1) by

mathematical modeling according to the criterion of optimality – the value of food digestibility. The choice of food digestibility as an optimality criterion is due to the fact that this characteristic as an integral function is responsible for a set of qualitative indicators of the product (nutritional, biological value, etc.).

In the minced composition of mutton and algae, the limiting amino acid is methionine and cystine, its amount is 94 % of its content in the "ideal" protein. At the same time, all minced binary compositions have a relatively high content of total protein, the amount of which ranges from 9.44 % (duck) to 22.26 % (beef). Moreover, the content of lipids in the amount of 6.52 % to 10.32 % and carbohydrates in the amount of 5.52 to 5.80 % is the advantage of these compositions. The high content of total protein, the presence of lipids and carbohydrates in minced meat compositions ultimately determine their relatively high energy value from 160.76 to 205.03 kcal per 100 g of product. The research results indicate the need to continue development in this direction.

It is possible to achieve the desired result by using products of natural origin (5, 6). The resulting meat-growing systems have a functional orientation and can

affect both the body as a whole and vital organs individually (7, 8). Recently, milk processing products have become increasingly widely used in the production of functional meat products (3). Of particular interest is the addition of a fermented milk product to the minced meat (9, 10). When it is added, the chemical composition changes, the nutritional value of the product increases, it is possible to form the properties of minced meat, giving the product a functional orientation. In the manufacture of dietary types of sausages, milk starter is specially added, which in turn gives the product a sour taste and a special aroma. The product acquires dietary properties (10-12). When developing new types of products, it is essential for consumers to evaluate the general characteristics of products, taking into account their organoleptic characteristics. To ensure the results of consumer evaluation, it is necessary to spend significant resources, which are not always available to medium and small food production enterprises. In addition, the lack of methods, procedures, computer programs hinder the promotion of modern methods of consumer testing in the domestic food industry, determines the need to find new approaches to the technology of products itself (13,14).

The quality of the raw meat is influenced by the property of muscle tissue. A. Sams (15) gives examples of how muscle reactions can damage or improve the quality of meat. Using microscopy techniques, A. Sams studied the changes that occur when muscles turn into meat. During the aging period, the activity of proteases in the components of the sarcomere is crucial for the maturation of meat, and then for softening. In both cases, microscopy was used to illustrate endogenous biochemical processes in muscles to produce tender meat, which facilitated understanding of the complexity of aging phenomena. The protease activity of poultry muscle tissue is also of interest to producers. The resulting ultrastructure of PSE meat of broiler chickens allows us to characterize the quality of the feedstock: pale, soft, exudative (16). This will facilitate the choice of processing methods when combining meat and vegetable raw materials in one functional product.

The influence of technological factors and the reaction of the environment is fundamental in a number of technologies in the development of new technical solutions. Thus, F. Leroy, J. Verluyten, L. Vuyst (17) proposed functional meat starter cultures to improve the fermentation of sausage products. Innovative technological techniques include the use of probiotic cultures in the fermentation of cured sausages (18), as well as the fermentation of sausages using the probiotic strain *Lactobacillus casei* LOCK 0900/M (19). The microstructure of meat and meat products, as well as their nutritional qualities, change when they are manufactured with an admixture of functional additives (20).

The structural approach largely clarifies which components of meat are responsible for its tenderness, moisture-retaining ability and appearance, as well as the processes occurring during processing. In the

Materials and methods

The research was conducted at the Department of Food Industry, Hotel Business and Service of the Rus-

sian Biotechnological University. The objects of research are the following types of meat raw materials: premium beef, semi-fat pork, lamb of the I category, broiler chicken fillet of the I category and duck of the I category, algae.

The following methods were used during the research:

- processing of laboratory data on a computer (automatic processing and analysis of laboratory tests);

- determination of the moisture binding capacity of meat (the method of centrifugation is based on the separation of the liquid phase under the action of centrifugal force from the object under study, located in a fixed position);

- determination of moisture retention capacity (the method is based on evaporation of moisture from the test sample using a special device);

- determination of the fat-holding capacity (in this method, a refractometer is used to determine the refractive index of the test sample);

- determination of emulsifying ability (to determine the emulsifying ability, a homogenized mixture of the test sample and refined sunflower oil is used, which is centrifuged);

- determination of indicators of biological value by the calculation method (the method is a group method, and is used to calculate the amino acid composition, identify limiting amino acids, estimate the average excess of the composition of essential amino acids and calculate the utility coefficient).

The limiting shear stress was determined by the magnitude of the greatest load and calculated by the formula (Eg./1/): $\sigma_0 = P_{max} / S$, /1/ where σ_0 — maximum shear stress/(kg/m²); P_{max} — maximum load/N; S — working surface area /m². The viscosity of the combined structured stuffing systems was determined by a RV-8 viscometer with a plane-parallel gap of the Volarovich system. Economic and mathematical methods and models of computer modeling according to the methodology of I.V. Orlova, V.A. Polovnikov (23). At the same time, arithmetic averages, average errors and the reliability of the main and compared indicators were determined. The statistical reliability of the main and compared indicators was calculated using the Student's criterion for the level of reliability (confidence probability $P = 0.90$) and the values of the number of degrees of freedom k (Eg. /2/): $k = n_1 + n_2 - 2$. /2/

Organoleptic evaluation of raw materials, minced meat and finished products was carried out by sensory analysis on a 5-point scale for each indicator (Rodina, Vux, 1994), the establishment of profiles of cutlets, medallions, balls, sticks by descriptors characteristic of this group of products: ISO 11035:1994; ISO 6658:1985 (currently ISO 6658-2016).

Results and Discussion

Thus, the results of the organoleptic evaluation obtained using questionnaires for paired comparisons revealed only a difference in specific organoleptic quality indicators of minced binary compositions prepared from raw meat with different amounts of algae. Organoleptic evaluation of them using a five-point scale made it possible not only to assess the quality level of minced bi-

nary compositions in points, but also to obtain mathematical models that allow determining the optimal values of factors – C, W, T.

The conducted studies allow us to conclude that the optimal values of the factors are:

- the content of algae in minced compositions is 30 %
- humidity – 5-60 %

- the duration of grinding – 6 min.

The results of organoleptic evaluation of the quality of minced binary compositions made according to optimal parameters C, W, T are presented on Fig. 1. they indicate a different level of quality of minced compositions from different meat raw materials. As can be seen, the limits of fluctuations in the assessment of their quality ranged from 92.6 to 97.6% (24-27).

Fig. 1. Organoleptic evaluation of minced binary compositions
1. beef + algae; 2. duck + algae; 3. lamb + algae; 4. chicken + algae; 5. pork + algae.

Comparative organoleptic evaluation showed a different level of quality of minced binary compositions, depending on the ratio of algae, meat improving in all major indicators in the following order: Y1, Y2, Y3, Y4, Y5.

After conducting an organoleptic evaluation and constructing mathematical models, the number of essential amino acids in minced binary compositions and their energy value were determined (Table 10).

Table 10.

Essential amino acids (A/(% protein)), amino acid score (C/(%)) and energy value(kcal/100 g) of minced binary compositions

Indicator	Stuffing composition				
	beef + algae	lamb + algae	pork + algae	duck + algae	chicken +algae
Mass fraction/% water	55.37	58.95	63.56	64.87	62.36
Protein	22.26	21.13	19.90	19.44	21.92
Lipids	9.79	10.02	6.80	6.23	6.22
Carbohydrates	5.68	5.80	5.78	5.57	5.52
ΣHAK/% protein	43.86 122	43.59 121	48.62 108	44.93 126	45.29 123
Isoleucine A C	4.70 118	4.84 121	6.38 160	4.63 116	4.98 125
Leucine A C	8.03 115	8.10 116	8.03 115	7.5 114	9.45 121
Lysine A C	8.50 155	8.37 152	9.70 176	8.37 152	8.30 151
Methionine + cysteine A C	3.51 102	3.30 94	4.21 120	3.99 114	3.58 102
Phenylalanine + Tyrosine L C	7.12 119	7.75 129	8.03 134	8.45 141	7.26 121
Threonine A C	4.98 125	4.50 113	5.19 130	5.12 128	4.63 116
Tryptophan A C	1.10 110	1.30 130	1.30 130	1.30 130	1.10 110
Valin A C	5.92 118	5.43 109	5.78 116	5.57 111	5.99 120
Energy value	205.03	202.95	167.95	160.76	169.80

The analysis of the results given in Table 10 shows that the number of essential amino acids in minced binary compositions obtained according to the optimal regime has significantly increased. Only in the minced lamb + algae composition, the limiting amino acid is methionine and cysteine. its amount is 94% of its content in the "ideal" protein.

At the same time, all minced binary compositions have a relatively high content of total protein, the

amount of which ranges from 9.44% (duck) to 22.26% (beef). Moreover, the content of lipids in the amount of 6.52% to 10.32% and carbohydrates in the amount of 5.52 to 5.80% is the advantage of these compositions.

The high content of total protein, the presence of lipids and carbohydrates in minced meat compositions ultimately determine their relatively high energy value from 160.76 to 205.03 kcal per 100 g of the product.

In the course of experimental studies, the dependences of structural and mechanical parameters of minced binary compositions, such as the ultimate shear stress, Viscosity, stickiness and VUS, on the duration of

grinding mixtures with an algae content in minced binary composition equal to 30% and a mass fraction of water of 50-60% were determined. The research results are presented at Fig. 2 – 4.

Fig. 2. The dependence of the limiting shear stress (σ_0) of minced binary compositions on the duration of grinding (τ) with the addition of 30% algae: 1 – duck; 2 – beef; 3 – chicken; 4 – lamb; 5 – pork

Fig. 3. The dependence of the viscosity (η) of minced binary compositions on the duration of grinding (τ) with the addition of 30% algae: 1 – duck; 2 – beef; 3 – chicken; 4 – lamb; 5 – pork

Fig. 4. Graphs of changes in stickiness (ζ) of minced binary compositions from the duration of grinding (τ) at 30% of algae: 1 – duck; 2 – beef; 3 – chicken; 4 – lamb; 5 – pork

As a result of the research, it was found that the degree of grinding and uniformity of minced binary compositions (collectively, consistency) depend on the duration of the grinding process. In turn, rheological parameters and water-holding capacity, which together determine the quality of the product, depend on the degree of grinding and uniformity of minced binary compositions.

Grinding improves the structure and consistency of minced compositions, increases their viscosity and stickiness, improves organoleptic characteristics. When minced meat is crushed, not only mechanical and chemical changes occur, causing the binding of water with proteins and contributing to the emulsification of fat. In muscle tissue, actomyosin is further cleaved into actin and myosin, molecules that absorb water better and are more easily converted into a soluble state than the actomyosin complex. Additional grinding increases the uniformity of the consistency of minced binary compositions and reduces the separation of moisture from them during heat treatment. As can be seen from the presented dependencies, there is an optimal grinding duration for each of the types of minced compositions, at which the structural, mechanical and organoleptic parameters are the best, which ensures high quality of the

product. However, longer grinding is accompanied by an increase in the temperature of the minced meat, which reduces the quality of the minced binary compositions and can lead to protein denaturation.

Two periods are characteristic of this process of grinding minced meat systems. In the first period, intensive mixing and cutting of muscle tissue particles of meat and algae occurs, while the total surface of the particles increases, moisture from free passes into surface-bound, a new structure is formed, characterized by high structural and mechanical properties. Extreme values of rheological indicators correspond to the extreme points of another indicator – water retention capacity.

In the second period of grinding and mixing of the components of minced compositions, due to an increase in the number of the smallest compositions, their aggregation, aeration of the mass and emulsification of fat, a secondary structure is formed, all indicators of which deteriorate. In order to establish the dependence of the effect of the grinding duration on the water-holding capacity of minced meat and minced binary compositions, studies were conducted, the results of which are given in Table 1.

Table 11.

Stuffing composition	Dependence of VUS /% on the duration of grinding (τ) of minced compositions								
	Duration of grinding (τ)/s								
	0	60	120	180	240	300	360	420	480
Beef	42.1±2.1	44.2±2.2	48.0	50.6	52.1	53.2	54.0±	54.	54.9
Beef + algae	45.0±2.3	49.8±2.1	±2.3	±2.4	±2.2	±2.4	2.4	8±2.1	±2.4
Pork	44.0±2.2	49.5±2.1	63.6	57.2	60.1	61.4	62.5±	63.	63.3
Pork + algae	44.0±2.2	49.5±2.1	±2.6	±2.3	±2.4	±2.6	2.6	0±2.4	±2.8
Lamb	50.0±2.4	53.2±2.4	55.3	59.3	62.0	64.0	66.0±	66.	66.8
Lamb + algae	50.0±2.4	53.2±2.4	±2.5	±2.5	±2.6	±2.7	2.6	5±2.6	±2.7
Chicken	49.6±2.2	54.1±2.3	64.8	67.1	69.3	70.4	71.2±	71.	72.1
Chicken + algae	49.6±2.2	54.1±2.3	±2.7	±2.8	±2.6	±3.1	3.1	7±2.9	±2.9
Duck	42.0±2.0	46.7±2.0	57.3	59.2	61.3	62.8	63.4±	64.	64.7
Duck + algae	42.0±2.0	46.7±2.0	±2.5	±2.4	±2.6	±2.8	2.3	0±2.8	±2.6
			59.0	62.0	63.5	64.3	65.4±	65.	66.2
			±2.4	±2.4	±2.5	±2.7	2.5	8±2.8	±2.6
			58.2	62.0	64.0	65.2	66.0±	66.	66.8
			±2.6	±2.5	±3.0	±2.7	3.0	3±2.6	±2.5
			61.3	64.5	67.3	69.1	70.0±	70.	70.6
			±2.8	±2.6	±3.0	±2.8	3.2	1±3.1	±2.9
			51.9	56.0	59.0	60.7	62.0±	62.	63.7
			±2.2	±2.3	±2.8	±2.8	3.1	4±2.6	±2.6
			62.0	64.4	67.8	69.8	71.0±	72.	72.5
			±2.6	±2.8	±3.0	±3.0	3.2	0±3.2	±2.9

The results are written as the mean \pm the standard deviation. The measurement error does not exceed 5% ($\varepsilon < 0.05$).

Analysis of the data on the dependence of the VUS on the duration of grinding (τ) for minced duck, beef, chicken, lamb, pork and minced compositions of these products with algae shows that with an increase in the duration of grinding, the VUS of minced meat and minced composition increases from 42 to 63.8% and from 52 to 72.6% (for minced duck and duck + 30% algae), respectively (24-27).

The conducted studies show that the addition of minced beef and seaweed in an amount of 30% by weight of raw meat contributes to an increase in the VUS of minced compositions by 10%.

At the same time, the grinding time τ can be determined by the following dependencies:

– for minced duck

$$\tau = 578.690 - 184.624 \cdot \ln(64.833 - \text{VUS}); \quad (13)$$

– for the stuffing composition duck + algae

$$\tau = 597.609 - 195.008 \cdot \ln(73.692 - \text{VUS}). \quad (14)$$

The analysis of the dependencies of the VUS of minced pork and the minced pork + algae composition shows that with an increase in the duration of grinding, the VUS also increases from 44 to 66.8% and from 56.3 to 72.1%, respectively. Studies have shown that the inclusion of minced pork and 30% algae by weight in minced meat can increase the VUS of the minced composition by 12%.

At the same time, the grinding time τ can be determined by the following dependencies:

– for minced pork

$$\tau = 554.270 - 174.507 \cdot \ln(68.264 - \text{VUS}); \quad (15)$$

– for the minced composition pork + algae

$$\tau = 490.333 - 174.325 \cdot \ln(72.938 - \text{VUS}). \quad (16)$$

Dependency analysis (Table 11) shows that minced beef, beef + algae, is also characterized by an increase in VUS depending on the duration of grinding.

For minced beef, these values increased from 42.1 to 54.9% and from 45.0 to 63.3%, respectively.

Thus, the inclusion of algae in minced beef allows you to increase the VUS of the product by 8-12%, respectively.

At the same time, the grinding time (τ) can be determined by the following dependencies:

– for minced beef

$$\tau = 519.183 - 188.917 \ln(65.792 - \text{VUS}); \quad (17)$$

– for the stuffing composition beef + algae

$$\tau = 491.243 - 189.436 \cdot \ln(67.008 - \text{VUS}). \quad (18)$$

Dependency analysis (Table 11) shows that minced lamb, mutton + algae, is also characterized by an increase in VUS depending on the duration of grinding. For minced lamb, these values increased from 50.0 to 64.7% and from 53.5 to 66.2%, respectively.

Thus, the inclusion of seaweed in minced lamb allows you to increase the VUS of the product by 3%, respectively.

At the same time, the grinding time τ can be determined by the following expressions:

– for minced lamb

$$\tau = 503.962 - 192.961 \ln(55.929 - \text{VUS}); \quad (19)$$

– for the minced composition lamb + algae

$$\tau = 507.431 - 174.0 \ln(64.262 - \text{VUS}). \quad (20)$$

The analysis of the dependence (Table. 11) shows that the minced chicken, chicken + algae, is also characterized by an increase in VUS depending on the duration of grinding. For minced chicken, these values increased from 49.6 to 64.7% and from 53.5 to 66.2%, respectively.

Thus, the inclusion of algae in minced chicken allows you to increase the VUS of the product by 2%, respectively.

In this case, the grinding time (τ) can be determined by the following expressions:

- for minced chicken
 $\tau = 503.962 - 197.961 \cdot \ln(55.929 - VUS)$; (21)
- for the minced composition chicken + algae
 $\tau = 507.431 - 171.44 \cdot \ln(64.262 - VUS)$. (22)

Calculations carried out using these expressions show that the duration of grinding minced binary compositions should be 5-6 minutes.

Consequently, for minced meat with a lower VUS, there is a higher VUS value after adding algae to the minced meat and, conversely, for minced meat with a higher VUS, there are lower

VUS values when algae is added to them.

Conclusions.

Thus, according to the results of the conducted studies, it was found that on the basis of regression analysis of the dependencies $Y_i = f(X_1, X_2, X_3)$, mathematical models of organoleptic evaluation of minced binary compositions were constructed depending on the amount of protein product added (algae), the mass fraction of moisture in minced binary compositions and the duration of their grinding. The binary compositions included premium beef meat, semi-fat pork, lamb of the I category, broiler chicken fillet of the I category and duck of the I category and algae in concentrations from 10 to 30%. In the studied vegetable minced meat with algae, the digestibility of the finished product increases by 10%.

It was found that minced meat with the addition of algae in an amount of 30% to the mass of meat raw materials contributes to an increase in the VUS of minced compositions by 10%. Organoleptic evaluation of cutlets, balls, medallions and sticks, carried out using a five-point scale, made it possible not only to assess the quality level of minced binary compositions, but also to obtain mathematical models that allow determining the optimal values of factors - concentration (C), mass fraction of moisture (W) and duration of grinding of the binary system (T). It was found that in minced binary compositions made according to the optimal regime, the number of essential amino acids significantly increased. Only in the minced composition of mutton and algae, the limiting amino acid is methionine and cystine, its amount is 94% of its content in the "ideal" protein. At the same time, all minced binary compositions have a relatively high content of total protein, the amount of which ranges from 9.44% (duck) to 22.26% (beef). Moreover, the content of lipids in the amount of 6.52% to 10.32% and carbohydrates in the amount of 5.52 to 5.80% is the advantage of these compositions. The high content of total protein, the presence of lipids and carbohydrates in minced meat compositions ultimately determine their relatively high energy value from 160.76 to 205.03 kcal per 100 g of product.

References

1. Mikhaleva EV, Reneva YA. Modeling of minced meat using vegetable mixtures. *Agrarian Bulletin of the Urals*. 2017; 11 (165): 32–41.
2. Karpunina LI, Kochneva SV. Development of combined minced meat semi-finished products for functional purposes. *Mat. International Scientific Conf. Kemerovo*. 2015; 309–310.
3. Skorokhodov DA, Yakupov FF, Dogareva

NG, Rebezov YM. Functional meat products. *Young scientist*. 2017; 9: 88-91.

4. Fedoseenko VA. Improvement of combined food products. *Mat. III International Student Scientific and Practical conf. Vladivostok*. 2017; 87–89.
5. Gayazova AO, Rebezov MB, Nesmeyanova OV. Functional meat products (patent search). *Economics and business. The look of the young*. 2015; 1: 312–315.
6. Okuskhanova E, Assenova B, Rebezov M, Yessimbekov Z, Zinina O. Mineral composition of deer meat pate. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*. 2016. 15 (3): 217–222.
7. Lyakhova NN. Production of boiled sausage using bioryazhenki: abstract. dis. Candidate of Technical Sciences: 05.18.04. Yekaterinburg. 2007; 149.
8. Giro TM, Davydova SV, Kozlov SV. Development of meat products for the prevention of cardiopathology. *Meat industry*. 2009; 2: 28–31.
9. Rebezov MB, Zinina OV, Nurymkhan GN, Nurgazezova AN, Smolnikova FH. Secondary raw materials of the dairy industry: current state and prospects of use. *Agroindustrial Complex of Russia*. 2016; 75(1): 150–155.
10. Rebezov MB, Zinina OV, Rebezov YM, Miroshnikova EP, Solovieva AA. Development of animal food products based on biotechnologies. *Agroindustrial Complex of Russia*. 2016; 23(2): 488–496.
11. Zinina OV, Kizatova MZ, Rebezov MB, Tretyak LN, Nabieva JS. Innovative planning of scientific developments in the food industry: textbook. *Almaty*. 2016; 148.
12. Mironova IV, Galieva ZA, Rebezov MB, Motavina LI, Smolnikova FH. Fundamentals of therapeutic and preventive nutrition: a textbook. *Almaty*. 2015; 241.
13. Potoroko IY, Tsurulnichenko LA. Formation of sensory characteristics of food products under the influence of sonochemistry effects. *Bulletin of the South Ural State University. Series: Food and Biotechnology*. 2014; 2(2): 27-32.
14. Potoroko I, Kalinina I, Popova N et al. The kinetics of formation of food products sensory characteristics under the effects sonochemistry. Program and book and abstracts of the 14th Meeting of the European Society of Sonochemistry. *Avignon*. 2014; 263-264.
15. Sams A. Meat quality during processing. *Poultry science. TLDR*. 1999
16. Wilhelm E, Magali Bernardes Maganhini, Hernandez-Blazquez F, Ida E, Shimokomaki M. Protease activity and the ultrastructure of broiler chicken PSE (pale, soft, exudative) meat. *Biology*. 2010.
17. Leroy F, Verleiten J, Wuist L. Functional meat starters to improve the fermentation of sausages. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*. 2012.
18. Andersen. L. Fermented Dry Sausages Produced with Probiotic Cultures: Proceedings of the 44th International Committee on Meat Science and Technology. 2012.
19. Trzaskowska M. Microbiological quality of raw fermented sausages with probiotic strain *Lactobacillus casei* LOCK 0900/M. 2012.

20. Shimokomaki M, Ida E, Talita Kato, Maika R. Pedrao, FAG Coro F, Hernandez-Blasquez J. Microstructure of meat and meat products and their nutritional qualities. Current contribution microscopy in advance. in science and technology: FORMATEX. 2012.
21. Offer G, Knight P, Jeacocke R, Almond R, Cousins Tony, Eley J, Parsons N, Sharp A, Starr R, Purslow P. Environmental Science Food Structure. 1989.
22. Shimokomaki M, Ida E, Kato Talita, Pedrão M, FAG. Coró F. Meat and meat products microstructure and their eating quality. Hernandez-Blazquez less Published. Biology. 2012
23. Orlova IV, Polovnikova VA. Economic and mathematical methods and models of computer modeling by methodology. 2007.
24. Vasyukova. AT, Vasyukov MV, Edwards RA, Makhmadaliev ES. Technologies of minced meat production based on the interchangeability of protein components of meat with algae. Priority and innovative technologies in animal husbandry – the basis of modernization of the agro-industrial complex of Russia: Collection of scientific articles. – Stavropol: AGRUS. 2019; 141-144. <http://doi.org/10.20914/2310-1202-2020-1-124-128>
25. Vasyukova AT, Edwards RA, Stukalov M, Shagarov SN, Boyko GY, Makhmadaliev ES. The influence of the degree of meat grinding on the flavor range of the product. Improving the nutrition of students in modern conditions: materials of the republican scientific and practical conference. – Donetsk: Publishing house DNUET. 2020; 31-32.
26. Vasyukova AT, Grokhovsky VA, Edwards RA, Makhmadaliev ES. Development of minced meat with dietary supplements from pumpkin seeds. Science and education – 2019: materials of the All-Russian scientific and practical conference. – Murmansk: Publishing House of MSTU. 2020: 155-160.
27. Vasyukova AT, Edwards RA, Vasyukov MV, Makhmadaliev ES. Amino acid composition of beef and lamb meat products. Actual issues of improving the technology of production and processing of agricultural products. 2020; 22: 252-255.